

BUDGET TRANSPARENCY PRACTICES IN SELECTED BARANGAYS IN THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNIT OF ANDA

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ABSTRACT

Budget transparency is crucial for effective governance, particularly within Local Government Units (LGUs), where communities rely on them for essential services such as infrastructure development, healthcare provision, and educational initiatives. LGUs, being the primary conduits of public service delivery, must uphold democratic values and maintain a high standard of accountability in managing public funds. This study explores the perceptions of both citizens and LGU employees in Anda, Bohol, regarding existing budget transparency practices and identifies potential areas for improvement. A self-made survey questionnaire was distributed to 116 citizens across four barangays and 100 LGU employees. The research employed a descriptive-comparative research design. Most respondents were aged 26–36, with a higher number of female respondents (122) compared to males (94). Data were analyzed using Frequency Count and Percentage, Weighted Mean, and the T-test Formula. Findings revealed a significant difference in perceptions between the two groups. Citizens indicated an “agree” level of transparency, with a sub-composite mean of 2.90, ranging from 2.81 to 3.02. In contrast, LGU employees showed a “strongly agree” level, with means ranging from 3.37 to 3.61. These results suggest that while budget transparency practices in LGU Anda are generally perceived as effective, LGU employees have greater confidence in these practices compared to citizens, likely due to their closer involvement in budgetary processes. This highlights the need for the LGU to improve public communication and engagement to bridge this perception gap.

Keywords: *Public administration, budget transparency, descriptive-comparative, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Budget transparency is a cornerstone of effective administration in the dynamic landscape of local governance. It ensures citizens' trust and reinforces democratic principles. As primary implementers of government policies and programs, LGUs manage critical services such as infrastructure, healthcare, and education, making transparency in financial operations indispensable.

Prijaković (2023) defines budget transparency as the provision of clear, complete, and accurate financial information that enables citizens to understand how public funds are allocated and used. This clarity builds public trust and legitimizes governance. However, as Mungiu-Pippidi (2023) emphasized, despite the recognized importance of transparency, global measurements remain lacking, making it difficult to assess their impact on corruption control and accountability, especially in developing countries.

Chen and Neshkova (2020) further noted that while the global call for government transparency is increasing, there is limited empirical evidence on how it shapes governance and decision-making. A gap also exists in identifying which aspects of the budget process are most critical for ensuring transparency. Similarly, Natision et al. (2022) observed in Indonesia that although decentralization empowered local governments, financial transparency remains a challenge in ensuring resources align with public needs.

In the Philippine context, Malitao et al. (2020) pointed out that managing local finances remains a challenge for LGUs, significantly impacting public perceptions of transparency. Diokno-Sicat et al. (2022) also underscored the need to improve programs like the Performance Challenge Fund (PCF), citing budget limitations and overlapping national programs.

Some LGUs continue to struggle with budget transparency, despite ongoing reforms. Upholding transparency enables LGUs to fulfill their democratic duties, foster trust, and empower citizens to engage in governance. It also safeguards against corruption, ensuring that public resources are directed toward the common good.

This study investigates how Anda's LGU maintains or enhances its budget transparency practices. It aims to evaluate transparency guidelines, accessibility of budget information, effectiveness of citizen engagement mechanisms, and thoroughness of financial reporting. Ultimately, the study seeks to determine how these practices contribute to citizen empowerment and accountability at the local level.

Research Questions

This study, conducted in fiscal year 2024, aimed to explore budget transparency practices in the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Anda. Specifically, it sought to: 1) determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: age; sex; and civil status; 2) assess the perceptions of both citizens and LGU employees regarding budget transparency practices in the LGU of Anda; and identify whether a significant difference exists between the perceptions of citizens and LGU employees concerning budget transparency.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-comparative research design. The researchers employed structured questionnaires to systematically identify, describe, and analyze relevant variables within the context of budget transparency in Anda's LGU.

Research Respondent and Locale

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Anda, located in the province of Bohol, Philippines. Anda is a coastal town situated approximately 100 kilometers from Tagbilaran City. It is known for its pristine white-sand beaches, crystal-clear waters, and diverse marine life. The town's natural beauty and its people's close connection to coastal resources made it a suitable setting for this study.

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Anda, Bohol—a coastal town approximately 100 kilometers from Tagbilaran City, known for its pristine beaches and marine biodiversity. Respondents included 116 citizens from four barangays (Bacong, Suba, Tawid, and Poblacion) and 100 LGU employees. A systematic random sampling technique ensured a representative and reliable sample, resulting in 216 participants.

A total of 216 participants took part in the study. These included 116 residents from four selected barangays—Bacong, Suba, Tawid, and Poblacion—and 100 employees from the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Anda. The respondents were chosen through a systematic random sampling technique to ensure that the gathered data accurately represented both the local community and the municipal workforce.

Research Instrument

A self-made questionnaire was utilized to gather data regarding the perceptions and experiences of the respondents on budget transparency practices. The questionnaire was designed based on relevant literature and aligned with the objectives of the study. To ensure the internal consistency and reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted, and the reliability coefficient was computed using Cronbach's Alpha. The

resulting Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.79, indicating acceptable reliability of the questionnaire items.

The instrument consisted of two parts: Part I: Demographic information (age, sex, civil status). Part II: A 10-item scale assessing budget transparency practices in the LGU of Anda, rated using a four-point Likert scale: (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Agree, and (4) Strongly Agree. The following statistical tools were employed to analyze the data: Frequency count and percentage – to describe the demographic profile of the respondents. Weighted mean – to assess the level of perception regarding budget transparency practices. T-test – to determine if a significant difference exists between the perceptions of citizens and LGU employees.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were employed to analyze the data:

- Frequency count and percentage to describe the demographic profile of the respondents.
- Weighted mean to assess the level of perception regarding budget transparency practices.
- T-test to determine if a significant difference exists between the perceptions of citizens and LGU employees.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the study on the level of budget transparency practices in selected barangays within the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Anda, Bohol. The findings are organized into three parts: (1) the demographic profile of the respondents, (2) the perceived level of budget transparency, and (3) the comparative analysis between citizen and employee perceptions. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and independent sample t-tests to determine differences in perceptions.

Demographic Profile of Respondents. The study involved a total of 216 respondents, comprising 116 citizens from four selected barangays (Bacong, Poblacion, Tawid, and Suba) and 100 LGU employees. Table 1 outlines their demographic characteristics in terms of age, civil status, and sex.

**TABLE 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents
(n = 216)**

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
1.1 Age		
15-25 years old	35	16.20
26-36 years old	51	23.61
37-47 years old	40	18.52
48-58 years old	42	19.44
59-69 years old	31	14.35
70-80 years old	15	06.94
81 years old and above	2	00.94
1.2 Civil Status		
Single	84	38.89
Married	108	50.00
Widow/Widower	21	09.72
Separated	3	01.39
1.3 Sex		
Male	94	43.52
Female	122	56.48

The majority of respondents were aged 26–36 years (23.61%), married (50%), and female (56.48%). The demographic composition provides a broad representation across age groups and civil status, contributing to the reliability of the perceptions gathered in this study.

Perceptions on Budget Transparency Practices. Respondents were asked to rate ten indicators of budget transparency using a 4-point Likert scale. Table 2 summarizes the responses of both citizens and employees, along with the computed weighted means and descriptive interpretations.

**TABLE 2. Perceived Level of Budget Transparency in Selected Barangays
(n = 216)**

Items	Citizens n=116		Employees n=100	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
1. The budgeting process of our local government unit is transparent and easily understandable.	3.02	Agree	3.61	Strongly Agree

2. The budgetary decisions made by our local government unit reflect the priorities of the community.	2.97	Agree	3.60	Strongly Agree
3. The local government unit effectively communicates how taxpayer's money is being utilized.	2.91	Agree	3.57	Strongly Agree
4. The local government unit provides explanations for any discrepancies or variations in budget expenditures.	2.91	Agree	3.53	Strongly Agree
5. The local government unit adequately discloses information about its budgetary performance and expenditures.	2.89	Agree	3.57	Strongly Agree
6. The budget information provided by our local government unit is easily accessible to the public.	2.88	Agree	3.44	Strongly Agree
7. The local government unit effectively solicits feedback from citizens regarding budget priorities and allocations.	2.86	Agree	3.37	Strongly Agree
8. Citizens have adequate opportunities to voice concerns or suggestions regarding the budget.	2.85	Agree	3.45	Strongly Agree
9. The local government unit provides timely updates on budget-related matters.	2.84	Agree	3.49	Strongly Agree
10. Decision-making regarding budget allocations and expenditures in our local government unit is transparent.	2.81	Agree	3.53	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	2.90	Agree	3.52	Strongly Agree

The overall mean for citizen respondents was 2.90, corresponding to the interpretation of "Agree". This suggests that, from the citizen's perspective, the LGU demonstrates a reasonable level of transparency, although not exemplary. In contrast, LGU employees reported a significantly higher mean of 3.52 or "Strongly Agree", indicating a much more favorable perception of transparency practices within their institution.

The most highly rated indicator for both groups was the transparency and clarity of the budgeting process (WM = 3.02 for citizens, WM = 3.61 for employees). Meanwhile, the least-rated items for citizens included transparency in allocation decisions (WM =

2.81), while employees gave the lowest score to the solicitation of citizen feedback (WM = 3.37).

These findings suggest a discrepancy between internal and external perceptions of transparency. Citizens acknowledge efforts at transparency but are more reserved in their assessments, possibly due to limited access to detailed budget documents or limited participation in budget-related decision-making.

This observation aligns with prior studies. Prijaković (2022) argued that transparent budgeting enhances public satisfaction and minimizes corruption. Similarly, Hu et al. (2020) highlighted that citizens' perceptions of transparency significantly influence their trust in local governance. However, Fortuna (2021) emphasized that actual citizen involvement, not just information availability, is crucial in achieving meaningful transparency.

Comparative Analysis of Perceptions. To determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between the perceptions of citizens and LGU employees, an independent samples t-test was conducted. The results are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3. T-Test Results Comparing Citizen and Employee Perceptions of Budget Transparency (n = 216)

Respondents	Mean Difference	T-Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Citizens	2.90	9.3107	.00001	Reject H ₀	Significant
Employees	3.52				

The t-test results revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($t = 9.3107$, $p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis of no difference in perception is therefore rejected. This suggests that LGU employees view their organization's budget transparency more favorably than the citizens do.

The difference in perception could be attributed to employees' access to internal processes and documentation, which are not as readily available to the public. Moreover, employees may have a vested interest in maintaining a positive organizational image, contributing to more favorable assessments. These results underscore the need for inclusive transparency mechanisms that not only publish financial data but also actively engage citizens in budget formulation, monitoring, and evaluation.

Van den Boogard et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of interactive transparency, wherein citizens are not merely passive recipients of information but are active participants in governance. Such an approach may help close the perception gap observed in this study.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study highlights a notable disparity in the perceptions of budget transparency between citizens and LGU employees in the Local Government Unit of Anda, Bohol. While both groups acknowledge a reasonable level of transparency, employees generally rate the practices more favorably than citizens, suggesting a gap in access to information and active citizen involvement.

The statistically significant difference between their perceptions underscores the need for the LGU to adopt more inclusive and interactive transparency mechanisms. Enhancing citizen engagement in budget processes and improving public access to detailed budget information can foster greater trust and accountability in local governance.

The study contributes to the growing body of literature emphasizing the role of citizen engagement in enhancing budget transparency and good governance. It also underscores the need for LGUs to critically assess and refine their current practices, moving beyond compliance and toward inclusive and participatory public financial management.

Recommendations

This study recommends that the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Anda, Bohol, enhance its budget transparency practices by strengthening public engagement mechanisms, improving the accessibility and clarity of budget information, and providing regular capacity-building initiatives for both citizens and LGU personnel. It also highlights the importance of institutionalizing monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the effectiveness of transparency efforts and suggests leveraging digital tools to broaden public access and participation. These actions are essential to fostering inclusive governance, strengthening public trust, and promoting sustainable local development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This quantitative survey-based study strictly adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection of respondents' rights and the integrity of the research process. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all respondents after explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their voluntary participation.

Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained by not collecting personally identifiable information, and all responses were treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes. The data were stored securely and analyzed objectively to avoid any form of bias or manipulation. Additionally, the study was conducted with the knowledge and approval of local authorities and complied with institutional ethical guidelines for research involving human participants.

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